

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT ACCESSIBILITY FOR SEMI-AMBULANCE DISABILITIES INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: *Inclusive education is a humane system to accommodate the needs of each individual according to his needs without discrimination therein. Disabilities are individuals who experience obstacles in performing daily activities on the environment, while someone who experience barriers to walking and mobility without tools called semi-ambulance person. If the environment in the area where he lives, or other common environment can't accommodate the mobility of conformity to its ability to meet its needs, it would be important to modify the environment that can be accessed easily, safely, and create a sense of comfort for disability semi ambulance. Things that need to be modified include the shape of the pavement, track conditions were not easy to damp, and not too steep, and exerts railing on the stairs. With the availability of physical accessibility in accordance with the capabilities of disabilities can provide equal opportunities to the community at large.*

Keyword : Accessibility Physical Environment, Disability, Inclusive Education.

INTRODUCTION

Equality, equality, status, rights and obligations as well as enhance the role of individuals who experience obstacles in their motor aspects (disability) will be very different from the acquisition, achievement, and the process to mobilize with a person in general (non-disabled). Disability is a term used in instruments International on inclusive education (Education for All) to someone who is experiencing barriers to either temporary or permanent Alimin, 2010. Related to Accessibility, someone who has a drag on the motor aspects will have difficulties in mobility. This is caused by the lack environmentally friendly motor skills possessed by each of the individual disability. Disability with resistance at aspects of the motor also has a wide range of categories, one of which is a semiambulance disabilities. According to Tarsidi (2011,pp.205), semi-ambulant disabilities is Quadriplegic who have difficulty walking but do not need a wheelchair. Thus, if the environment is not friendly to the conditions experienced by the disabilities semi-ambulant, it is certain that these individuals will experience the trauma of that environment, thus indirectly also affect the psychological of the individual, and will also have an impact on their daily activities.

According to Tarsidi (2008,pp.2) is the physical accessibility of the

physical environments that persons with disabilities can be approached, entered, or bypassed, and persons with disabilities are able to use the area as well as the facilities contained therein without assistance.

Thus the demanding environment disabilities using physical abilities if they want to access it, then it must do modifications or adjustments to the physical environment of the capabilities it has, so that persons with disabilities semi-ambulant can perform daily activities without assistance related to the accessibility of the physical environment according to his ability, as well as another possibility could impact the development potential in achieving the independence of a semiambulant disabilities if the physical environment have followed suit its needs.

According to the definition of seminar Agra and Policy South Africa in 1998, which was adopted in the South African White Paper on Inclusive Education, said at one point is enabling structures and systems to meet the needs of all, and a dynamic process that is constantly evolving in accordance with the culture and context, as well as a wider strategy to promote an inclusive society. (Tarsidi, 2002,pp.15).

It is intended to recognize and appreciate the differences possessed by each individual. So that disability and non-disability is no barrier in

terms of acceptance. Tarsidi (2002,pp.37) also defines inclusive education and inclusive itself, both meanings have principles and content of the same value in general, namely recognition, service, award-wide acceptance of difference. However, these definitions are constantly evolving in line with the deepening of reflections on the existing practice, as well as the emergence of new cases serve as the basis with the aim of achieving an inclusive society. The perspective on inclusive education in general to interpret the accessibility of the physical environment is paramount for a disability who have difficulty in walking, but without using a wheelchair. Thus there is concern about the impact that occurs when the physical environment can't be accessed by semi-ambulant disabilities and how the physical environment can be accessed by semiambulant disabilities. Issues related on accessibility to the physical environment as a means used by the disabled, especially the semiambulant in the activities of mobility there are problems with how important accessibility of the physical environment such for disability semiambulant, as well as the direct impact caused if it to materialize such accessibility is not reached for some people it is still regarded as exaggerated care and stigmatization. It is based on the lack of public understanding of the capabilities, constraints and needs of each individual is different. Especially the needs of the more complex disabilities. In addition, concerning about accessibility for disability also have declarations based instruments convention by various parties from several countries related to inclusion for disabled and non-disabled.

CONTENT

According to WHO (World Health Organization) defines disability as follows:

“Disability is a “restriction or lack (resulting from an impairment) of ability to perform an activity in the manner or within the range considered normal for human being “It describes a functional limitation or activity restriction caused by an impairment.

Disabilities are descriptions of disturbances in function at the level of the person. Examples of disabilities include difficulty in seeing, speaking or hearing, difficulty in moving or climbing stairs, difficulty grasping, reaching, bathing, eating and toileting”

Based on the above definition is the inability of a person to perform activities such as people in general, as the result of damage to the body that affect the function of the body, thus the result of internal disorder or biological in such individuals have an impact on the ability to perform daily activities.

International Instruments which have declared equal rights and equality as well as the basic rules on accessibility contained in the PBB Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), (Tarsidi 2011,pp.202). The Convention also supports the realization of the modification of the physical environment for semi-ambulant disabilities. The cause of persons with disabilities semi-ambulant difficulties in mobilizing affected by several factors, namely: the causes of the barriers experienced by individuals themselves and several factors caused by the environment.

Participation in the framework of equality of opportunity is with the realization of accessibility in each State, the State's duty one of them is recognizing the importance of accessibility in the process of the equalization of opportunities in all community activities. According to the Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities is, each State to introduce programs of action to create a physical environment that is accessible to disabled and non-disabled as well as the availability of support availability access to the physical environment. Regarding access to the physical environment, States must also take steps to remove obstacles to participation in the physical environment such and such measures such as the development of standards and guidelines and considerations for enacting legislation in order to ensure accessibility to various areas of life in society. Countries must also ensure the actualization of standards in the application of the physical environment, and other parties who are professionally involved in the design and construction of the physical environment, have access to adequate information about the policy on disabilities as well as measures to create accessibility.

Accessibility requirements should also be included in the design and construction of the physical environment from the beginning to the design process. As well as support from organizations that fight for equal rights of persons with disabilities in an effort to support the realization of the accessibility of the physical environment, in the development of standards and norms for disability also must be consulted by the organization to the parties associated professionals. If organizations want to be involved or engaged directly by the government, it should be involved from an early stage of development projects of facilities and infrastructures of the physical environment. So as to create the accessibility that fits the needs of the individual.

The involvement of individuals with disabilities semi-ambulant and family parties must also be included in the development of

accessibility standards of the physical environment. This is because in order to maximize the accessibility requirement standards in the creation of the physical environment.

Assessment of creating accessibility of the physical environment for semi-ambulant disabilities have several stages; The first motion capability assessment tool, generally semiambulant person's disability impaired motor development and mobility intelligence, either in part or as a whole. A wide variety of physical and intellectual disabilities semi-ambulant person, requires careful management in identifying its strengths and weaknesses. This is important in the effort to determine what is needed to carry out mobilization activities according to their ability and circumstances. The assessment is done on a semi-ambulant person's disability was conducted to determine the state of posture, body balance, muscle strength, mobility, intelligence, and palpability. Assessment tool used for semiambulant person's disability, as follows; Finger goniometer (measuring tool-regional joint motion), Flexiometer (gauges spasticity), Plastic goniometer (measuring tool joints made of plastic), Physical Exercise Equipment/Motion Train. In general, semi-ambulant person's disabilities experience obstacles in moving yourself (ambulation), and coordination/balance of the body. In order for semi-ambulant disabled person can perform activities of daily living necessary exercise. Tools that can be used can be: Pulley Weight (to strengthen the hand muscles and abdomen), Kanavel Table (for muscle strengthening hand, wrist and fingers), squeeze Ball (for power drills wringing hands), Self Development Tool.

The assessment was conducted to determine the ability, barriers or difficulties experienced and the needs of the individual. Thus obtained profile as a follow-up to provide services in accordance with the needs and the potential that can be developed.

The cause of that comes from the individual is based on history of disability they experienced since birth or accident that affects the motor system disorders. The cause can also be caused by viruses or bacteria at the time of the incident in the womb and the birth process. Someone with resistance at motor system also has some disturbances in the body that lead to limb can't make it work, or can make it work, but it takes longer than non-physical disabilities. Some motor barriers faced by persons with disabilities semi-ambulant:

i. Muscle stiffness or muscle tension, causing some muscles become stiff, slow movements and awkward.

- ii. Interference on one arm, which can be the left arm or right arm.
- iii. Wilting on one leg muscles, can the right foot or left foot.
- iv. Wilting in the muscles of the left leg and left arm, or vice versa, but still able to walk, though with the help hold one of member of gestures to support other body movements in order to move.

Barriers experienced by semi-ambulant disabilities will be very difficult when it will perform its activities. Thus the need for easiness that can support the activities mobilize. As has been described in several international conventions that guarantee to every state for the nation or people experiencing barriers to be provided with access to disability-related prevalence, so the semi-ambulant disabilities can perform activities such as people in general.

The impact if not done modifications to the environment that can accommodate the needs of semi-ambulant disabilities, it will affect the development of the system of the individual motor movement. One of the effects that can be caused by semi-ambulant disabled if the physical environment can't be realized is the trauma of the environment. This trauma will affect the individual's knowledge of the scope of these locations, so that one's limited knowledge of the information about the room. Therefore, in the fulfillment of their needs for someone with motor barriers can participate actively in community life. Contained in the regulations that have been agreed by several countries in the conventions that have been held that as a general instruments affirmed the equality of rights in social skills related to diversity without discrimination, including the ability of one's ability to perform activities of mobility.

Viewpoint in inclusive settings is acceptance and respect for differences is also used as a cornerstone in understanding the needs of a person related to the realization of equality in life to society thus one's response to the needs of each individual are different will be able to continue to develop theories that already exist in the perspective of inclusion.

The compensation can be given to persons with disabilities semi-ambulant is the accessibility of the physical environment that is tailored to the needs of each individual. Thus, the standard which is based on the capabilities that can reduce or eliminate these barriers. So the potentials that can be developed by the individual will appear.

Technical requirements and accessibility for supporting capability that has been owned by the semi-ambulant persons with disabilities are as follows: Technical requirements and accessibility

for supporting capability that has been owned by the semi-ambulant persons with disabilities are as follows.

Vehicle parking area reserved for persons with disabilities semi-ambulant, because there are also individuals who are able to use tools like transportation in general, transportation tool modification and unmodified. Such individuals do modifications to the transportation tool it uses, but is also supported by an environment that can give the individual access to through the neighborhood. Because when people are descended from the vehicle it uses and then to reach the intended location is too far or beyond the limits of its ability, the barriers will increasingly impact on other aspects. Thus the distance of the parking area, the condition of the parking area, as well as the capacity of the parking area should also be in the accounts in accordance with the abilities of the individual.

Railing, compensation balance when standing or walking, it will be very influential at the time of mobilization activities on the physical environment.

The lift, which can be used by individuals by providing a place to sit in the elevator, so that by the time the elevator up or down, someone who experienced obstacles in their motor can wait to sit down and not worry about being overcrowded, and also the placement of the same key used near the elevator door was also placed near areas used semi-ambulant disabilities.

Stairs, shape and size on each rung wider and not steep, so that the individual can be through the area to reach the destination that want it.

The floor area of the road reserved for semi-ambulant disabilities, areas that are not slippery conditions and not humid and dry quickly will be very helpful when the individual is running. It is based on the abilities of the person and his needs. Ability to prioritize on his balance.

Sidewalks, for non-disabled users allowed to get through these tracks that have been provided by the GOI. But for semi-ambulant disabilities will find it difficult to pass through. This happens because not reconciled with the track conditions for semi-ambulant disabilities users. Then the condition of the pavement was changed based on the needs of semi-ambulant disabilities.

Doors, size and operational standards needed so that persons with disabilities and nondisabled can pass through it without any worries. Automatic door too quickly duration will also lead to the individual's difficulties in accessing the destination location that will be passed.

Table 1- profile barriers

No.	Activity	Barriers
1	Walk up the stairs and down the stairs without rails	Fall accidentally
2	Walking on the sidewalk descending and ascending without rail	slip
3	Toilets without toilet seat	Difficulties in activity defecation and urination
4	The elevator without a seat and rail	Fatigue when standing and crowding in the elevator
5	Walking on wet floor	Slipping while walking
6	Walking through the narrow building size	Difficulty in walking
7	Parking Area distant destination location	Fatigue when it will travel a distance at the destination location

Based on the profile barrier above, it can be assumed disability semi-ambulant persons with disabilities will experience difficulties when going to mobilize, and some individuals will feel frustrated the physical environmental conditions. Hence the importance of accessibility in the physical environment so that a semi-ambulant disabilities can through these locations.

Technical accessibility requirements must also be specified as a standard design that can be made by those professionals and organizations in realizing the accessibility of the physical environment, following the technical requirements; Basic size room (Essence)
 Basic size of three dimensions (length, width, height), which refers to the size of an adult human body, the equipment used, dang space required to accommodate movement.
 (Requirements)
 The first: Basic size that is determined by considering the function of the building, a building with a function that allows used by many people at once, such as meeting halls, cinemas, etc., should use the maximum base size.

The second: the minimum and maximum base size used in these guidelines, can be increased or decreased along the principles of accessibility can be achieved. Pedestrian Paths (Essence) groove that is used for walking or semi-ambulant disabilities, which was designed based on the needs of people to move safely, comfortably and unobstructed. (Requirements)

- (1) Surface
The road surface must be stable, strong, weather resistant, textured smooth but not slippery. Avoid connection or bumps on the surface, even if forced to exist, the height should be no more than 1.25 cm. When using the carpet, the edges should be firm and have a permanent trim.
- (2) Tilt
The maximum slope of 60 outside the building and 70 in the building and at every distance of 9 m recommended are stopping for a break.
- (3) Areas of rest/landing
Mainly used to help the road users of semi-ambulant disabilities
- (4) Lighting
Ranged from 50-150 lux depending on the intensity of use, hazard and safety needs.
- (5) Treatment
Needed to reduce the possibility of accidents.
- (6) Drainage
Made perpendicular to the direction of the path with a maximum depth of 1.5 cm, is easily cleaned and kept away from the edge of the hole placement ramp.
- (7) Size
The minimum width is 120 cm pedestrian lane to lane unidirectional and 160 cm in both directions. Pedestrian path should be free from trees, signs and objects that prevented a complementary way.
- (8) Edge Protection
It is important for the termination of vehicle wheels and sticks blind towards a dangerous area. But the defense made a minimum of 10 cm height and a width of 15 cm along the pedestrian path. Including pedestrian pavements, but its location on the edge of the highway. For pavement floor surface should be in the same lane cultivated high street.
Parking area
(Essence)
Braille is the parking of vehicles driven by semiambulant disabilities, so it requires a larger place for up and down, rather than the usual vehicle parking lot. While the area to raise and lower passenger (Passenger-Loading Zones) is a place for all passengers, including the semi-ambulant disabilities up and down from the vehicle and the distance between the parking and the location is not far away destination.
(Requirements)

(1) Vehicle Parking Facility:
The first; Parking place semi-ambulant disabilities located on the shortest route toward the buildings/facilities at the destination, with a maximum distance of 60 meters.

The second; If the parking lot is not directly related to the building, for example on the parking park and other open places, the park should be placed as close as possible to the entrance gate and pedestrian path. The third; Parking area should have enough free space around it so that wheelchair users can easily enter and exit the vehicle.

Fourth special parking area semi-ambulant disabilities characterized by symbol/ parking sign with disabilities semi-ambulant applicable.

Fifth: In the parking lot of semi-ambulant disabilities are provided ramp sidewalk on both sides of the vehicle.

Sixth: The parking space has a width of 370 cm to 620 cm parking for single or double parking and is connected to the ramp and the road to the other facilities.

(2) The raising and lowering Passengers: First, the minimum depth of the area up and down passengers from the road or busy traffic lane is 360 cm and a minimum length of 600 cm.

Second, Equipped with ramps, pedestrian paths and signs Disabilities.

Third, the maximum slope of 50 with a flat surface in all sections.

Fourth, given the signs of Disability used to simplify and differentiate with similar facilities to the public.

Door

(Essence)

The door is part of a site, building or space is a place to get in and out which is generally equipped with a cover (door).

(Requirements)

(1)The gate Palm building must be easily opened and closed by a semi-ambulant disabilities.

(2)The exit/main entrance has a width of at least 90 cm aperture, and the doors are less important to have at least 80 cm wide openings.

(3)In the area around the entrance ramp avoided wherever possible presence or difference in height of the floor. (4) Types of doors that use is not recommended:

First, the sliding door Second, the doors are heavy and difficult to open/close.

Thirdly, the door with two doors are small. Fourth, the door is open in both directions ("push" and "pull")

(5)The use of automatic doors preferably are sensitive to the danger of fire. The door should not be opened fully in a faster time of 5 seconds and is easy to close again.

- (6) Avoid the use of the slippery floor around the door.
- (7) The tools automatic door closers need to be installed so that the door can close completely, due partly open door can harm people with disabilities.
- Ramp**
 (Essence)
 Ramp is a circulation path which has a field with a certain slope, as an alternative for people who can't use stairs
 (Requirements)
- (1) The slope of a ramp inside the building should not exceed 70, the slope calculation does not include prefix or suffix ramp (cumb ramps / landing). While the slope of a ramp which is beyond the maximum of 60 buildings.
- (2) The horizontal length of the ramp (with a slope of 70) should not be more than 900 cm. Long ramp with a lower slope can be longer.
- (3) The minimum width of the ramp is 95 cm without a safety edge, and 120 cm with a safety edge. To ramp which is also used both for pedestrians and freight services should be considered carefully in width, so that it can be used for both functions, or the separation ramp with its own function.
- (4) Front panel (landing) on a prefix or suffix of a ramp should be free and flat so it is likely at least to turn a wheelchair with a minimum size of 160 cm.
- (5) A flat surface prefix or suffix of a ramp should have a texture that is not slippery good time when it rains.
- (6) The width of the edge of the seat ramp (low curb) 10 cm, designed to block the wheelchair wheels so as not to fall in or out of the path of the ramp. When directly adjacent to the public road traffic or intersection should be made so as not to interfere with the general way.
- (7) Ramp must be illuminated with lighting ramp sufficient to help users ramp at night. Lighting is provided on parts of the ramp which has a height of the surrounding ground surface and the dangerous parts.
- (8) Ramp should be equipped with a handle propagation (handrail) guaranteed strength with the appropriate height.
- Stairs**
 (Essence)
 Facilities for the vertical movement and is designed taking into account the size and slope of the ground and climbs with adequate width.
 (Requirements)
- (1) Must have a foothold and climb dimension of uniform size.
- (2) Must have a slope of less than 600.
- (3) There is no hollow climbs stairs that can harm users.
- (4) Must be equipped with handles propagation (handrail) minimum on one side of the ladder.
- (5) The handle vines should be easy to handle with a height of 65-80 cm from the floor, free from disturbing construction element, and the edges should be well rounded or deflected by the floor toward the wall or pole.
- (6) The handle vines must be increased in length at the ends (peak bottom) with 30 cm.
- (7) For the stairs located outside the building, should be designed so that no rain water that pooled on the floor.
- Lift**
 (Essence)
 The lift is a mechanical-electrical tool to assist vertical movement in the building that is used specifically for persons with disabilities or who doubles as the freight elevator.
 (Requirements)
- (1) For buildings over 5 floors, at least one lift accessible fruit should be on the path of accessible and meet the technical standardsselling.
- (2) Tolerance of differences in advance storey building with a floor space face a maximum lift of 1.25 mm.
- (3) The corridor / lobby elevator.
 First, the intermediary space that used to await the arrival of the lift, as well as to accommodate passengers who just got out of the lift, should be provided. The width of this room is a minimum of 185 cm, and depending on the configuration of the existing space. Second, Placement buttons that display easily visible and accessible.
 Third, the outer panels containing button elevator should be installed in the middle of the room or hall elevator lobby with a height of 90-110 cm from the floor face of the building.
 Fourth, the panel of elevator buttons mounted at a height of 90-120 cm from the face of the floor space elevator.
 Fifth, all buttons on the panel must be equipped with Braille panels, which are installed without disturbing the usual panel. Sixth, there are indicators addition to voice, screen/display that visually represents the position of the elevator should be installed in the control panel and above the doors, both inside and outside the elevator (hall / corridor)
- (4) Space Elevator.
 First, the size of the space elevator must be able to load a wheelchair user, starting from the entrance through the door of the lift, twist, reach key panel and lift out the door.
 Minimum net size of the space elevator is 140cm x 140cm.
 Second, space elevators must be equipped with a handle propagation (handrail) continuously on three sides.
- (5) The elevator door.
 First, the minimum time for the elevator doors to remain open for answering a call is 3 seconds.

Second, the mechanism of opening and closing doors should be such that it provides sufficient time for persons with disabilities, especially to get in and out easily. For that lifts must be equipped with photo-electric sensor mounted at the appropriate height.

Toilet

(Essence)

The sanitary facilities are accessible to everyone, including the semi-ambulant disabilities

(Requirements)

- (1) Toilet or accessible public toilets should be equipped with a display signs for "persons with special needs (PBK)" on the outside.
- (2) The toilets or public toilets should have sufficient space
- (3) The height of the toilet seat must fit
- (4) Toilet or small rooms should be equipped with a handle propagation (handrail) which has a position and height adjustable handle and accommodate for someone with physical limitations.
- (5) The location of the tissue paper, water, tap water or shower (shower) and paraphernalia such as soap and hand dryers should be installed such that is easy to use by people who have physical limitations
- (6) Lever faucets should be installed on the sink.
- (7) Materials and adjustments need to be non-slip floor.
- (8) The door must be opened to facilitate easy for wheelchair users to open and close.
- (9) The keys toilet or bolt selected so that could be opened from the outside in case of emergencies.
- (10) In places easily reached, such as in the entrance area, it is recommended to provide emergency lighting button (emergency light button) if at any time a power outage occurs.

Environment Highway

(Essence)

Facilities on the highway that is used to provide information, directions, marker or pointer for persons with disabilities. In addition, to provide security and comfort in mobility for semiambulant disabilities.

(Requirements)

- (1) The use of signs are especially needed on: First, direction and purpose pedestrian pathways. Second, direction and destination city transportation lines. Third, place crossings, pedestrian bridges. Fourth, Disabled parking Directions to the roads. Fifth, facility names and place.
- (2) Terms signs are used: First, in the form of signs and symbols mark internationally. Second, the signs that apply specific methods Parks or Green Open Space

(Essence)

Facilities on the highway that is used to provide information, directions, marker or pointer for persons with disabilities. In addition, to provide safety and comfort in mobility for persons with disabilities semi-ambulant

(Requirements) (1) The use of signs are especially needed on:

First, direction and purpose pedestrian path
Second, direction and destination city transportation lines.

Third, place crossings, pedestrian bridges. Fourth, Disabled parking Directions to the roads.

Fifth, facility names and place.

- (2) Terms signs are used: First, in the form of signs and symbols mark internationally.

Second, the signs that apply specific methods

Equality and equal rights to the opportunity to enjoy the environment is an activity required by each individual related to the fulfillment of their needs.

Needs semi-ambulant persons with disabilities to get equal treatment with nondisability is to accommodate the needs in the activities of mobility is to modify the physical environment in order to access, so that it can be passed by a semi-ambulant disabilities.

Persons with disabilities semi-ambulant considered privileged part of the population, it is not true, they just want to get the same opportunities as non-disabled, but according to ability.

The accessibility of the physical environment is important for disability semiambulant, this is related to the principle of humanity which has also been listed by the government of Indonesia in the Indonesian Government Regulation No. 43 Year 1998 on Efforts to Increase Social Welfare of Persons with Disabilities, Article 1 Paragraph 3, which reads "equal opportunity is a state which provides opportunities for people with disabilities to have the same opportunity in the aspect of life and livelihood ", and then in paragraph 2" is the convenience provided accessibility for people with disabilities in order to achieve equality of opportunity in all aspects of life and livelihood ". Regulations have been made by the government may be invoked in the understanding of the needs are based on each individual's ability semiambulant disabilities.

Inclusive education perspective in principle is put easiness for persons with disabilities, especially in the aspect of accessibility is very essential position against human values. Persons with disabilities in inclusive education perspective is as a source to continue to develop the values the principles contained therein, for persons with disabilities not just as beneficiaries of

accessibility, they also as a resource to continue to develop theories of inclusiveness.

Presentation on accessibility standards in the physical environment that can be passed by a disability have also become part of the principle of the inclusive perspective. Based on theories of inclusive education to create an inclusive society has been described International instruments agreed upon by the governments.

According to UNICEF on the State of Children in the World in 2013, said that to realize the promise of equity through inclusion requires action to ratify and implement the Convention on the Rights of persons with disabilities, to combat discrimination and raise awareness of disability among the general public, decision makers, and those who provide services for disability, coordinate services in all sectors in order disabilities can move like people in general. Thus proving to all national and global efforts towards the fulfillment of the right to disability in mobility on the physical environment and accessibility for disability.

The convention states that a person with disabilities have the same rights as the public in general. Although the PBB Convention on the Rights of the Child in 1989 does not directly assert the accessibility to persons with disabilities, but there are rules in the form of Articles that overshadow all the chapters: chapters in section 2 (28) "non-discriminatory", and article 6 of the "right to survival and thriving", Tarsidi (2002:15). About Accessibility is also confirmed in the CRPD (Convention on the Right of Persons with Disability) in article 9 paragraph 1 of accessibility, it is stated that in order to pursue the rights of persons with disabilities to participate fully in all aspects of life and can be independently in fulfilling their needs , governments in every country undertake the necessary steps to ensure access by persons with disabilities, with one of them on the physical environment, Sholeh (2015:313). While in paragraph 2, in each State shall take appropriate measures, such as: Develop, promulgate and monitor the implementation of minimum standards and guidelines for the accessibility of facilities and services open or provided to the public, Sholeh (2015:313). This is based on safety for the disabled to equate the right to enjoy public service and fulfillment of the needs of the individual.

Institutions UNDP (United Nations Development Program) under the auspices of UN quoted the text of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 4 of 1997, Article 1, paragraph 1, of the definitions with smallpox, as follows;

“Disabled person is someone who has physical and/or mental abnormality, which could disturb or be seen as obstacle and constraint in performing

normal activities, and consisted of: a) physically disabled, b). mentally disabled, and c). physically and mentally disabled”

Based on the above quote, is someone with a physical or mental barriers that affect the activity as people in general.

The Indonesian government has also made Law No. 4 1997 Article 7 and stated that the government and or society are obliged to seek the realization of the rights of persons with disabilities. Then also in article 10, paragraph 1 and 2 of Act 4 of 1997 has been declared, for persons with disabilities are given the opportunity in all aspects of life and livelihood are implemented through the provision of accessibility. While in paragraph 2 more on providing an environment that access so that disability can participate directly in the community at large.

The principle of accessibility has four points, namely; The first principle is convenience, that is, everyone disability and non-disability can reach a destination through the physical environment with ease. The second is the principle of the principle of utility, meaning that anyone can use and take advantage of the environment to achieve a goal location. The third principle of which is the principle of safety, meaning that at the time through the physical environment to provide security for its users (disability and non-disability). The principle of the fourth is the principle of independence, meaning that a person can be through the physical environment and reaching a destination location without the help of others.

So clearly that the principles in the educational inclusive perspective have to accommodate the needs of disability within its rights without exception to the accessibility of the physical environment that can support the mobility activity in daily life. At the convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities also asserted that in an inclusive education perceptive accommodated to accessibility must also be considered. This is because the equal rights to the achievement of equality. Also as a support in the fulfillment of the needs of each individual.

Mobilization activities undertaken by semi-ambulant disabilities will be made to feel safe, comfortable, and easy to do or be passed if the physical environment provides accessibility according to his ability, and accessibility of the physical environment can also be used as prevalence for barriers they experienced. Because of the impact if the physical environment can't be accessed or difficulty when, the barriers experienced will be more complex. Thus, the importance of accessibility to the physical environment for semi-ambulant disabilities in inclusive education perspective.

CONCLUSION

Understanding of the semi-ambulant disabilities based on the capabilities, constraints or difficulties, and needs to make the runway interpretations of the importance of accessibility to the physical environment for semi-ambulant disabilities.

Accessibility has been declared with instruments convention by several countries, including Indonesia, so implementation should also be accomplished in accordance with the conditions of semi-ambulant disabilities. In the perspective of inclusive education, accessibility as a principle that there should be and implemented, so that the needs of individuals with disabilities semi-ambulant be met and they can actively participate in social activities, as well as prevalence to the impact that can be caused by obstacles and difficulties experienced, by Therefore accessibility to the physical environment is very important to implement affecting the fulfillment of the right to equality semi-ambulant disabilities. to be able to perform daily activities when mobilized on the physical environment.

RECOMMENDATION

In order for semi-ambulant disabilities can move freely in the mobility it needed accessibility physical environment, so it is very important accessibility of the physical environment was created for semi-ambulant disabilities.

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